

The Impact of Strategic Environment on Indonesian Arms Procurement

Avira Durrotul Rasyida¹, I Nengah Putra Apriyanto¹, George Royke Deksino¹

Defense Industry, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Jakarta, Indonesia;

Abstract: In supporting the minimum essential force (MEF) program, Indonesia tries to fulfill weapons by procuring weapons. Procurement of weapons carried out by Indonesia is not only from within the country, but also from abroad. Procurement of weapons in Indonesia is carried out by implementing the applicable provisions and regulations. the process of procuring defense weapons will always be influenced by external factors. The strategic environment in the procurement of weapons is an important factor in procurement. The aspects used are political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, environmental and law. The method used is descriptive qualitative.

Keywords: Procurement; offset; defense industrial policy; strategic environment;

I. Introduction

Indonesia is an archipelagic country with the fourth most population in the world. Its area is 5,193,250 km² with a total island are 17,504 islands. Indonesia strategic geographical condition is a challenge for the government to build defense and security. Development of defense posture, Indonesia considers geopolitical and geostrategic factors, as well as the characteristics of the country in the form of an archipelago and wide territorial sea. This condition allows the emergence of various kinds of threats both on land, sea and air. In conquer threats and develop defense posture, Indonesia must meet the needs of TNI (Indonesian military) which has been stipulated in the Minimum Essential Force (MEF) program. The fulfillment of arms is carried out by domestic or foreign procurement. The procurement of weapons and services are included in the strategic activities, which mean arms procurement is implementation of defense logistics activities.

Military and defense needs, have to be balanced with the development of weapons technology and modernization. Modernization can be done by arms trade or joint development between foreign defense industry as kwon as a defense offset. Activities for the procurement of goods and services are part of strategic activities. This is because procurement is an important part as a source of supply chain. Indonesia arms procurement policies prioritize local products. However, if the domestic defense industry has not been able to supply these needs, it will use foreign products, this is in accordance with the regulation of the minister of defense No. 17 of 2014 concerning the mechanism for the procurement of defense equipment. In the procurement of foreign defense equipment, the domestic defense industry must involve the trade balance mechanism or the fulfillment of local content and defense offsets as stated in Law No. 30 of 2015. Arms procurement certainly involves two countries, between buyer and seller country. Therefore, in this research will see how strategic environmental aspects and offset policy affect the arms procurement.

II. Literature Review

2.1 Strategic Environment in Procurement

In every foreign arms procurement, the strategic environment greatly influences the running of the defense offset program. The strategic environment also has an external influence on the procurement carried out. This is because the strategic environment will have an impact on contract agreements between the two countries, both buyers and sellers. Determination of strategic environmental aspects based on Political, Economic, Socio-Cultural, Technology, Environment, and Law aspects. These aspects were confirmed when interviews were conducted with the informants.

The political aspect examines the political conditions or policies that may have an impact on procurement. Not only reviewing the impact for the current time, the political aspect also tries to predict what will happen in the future. The economic aspect examines economic issues that may affect procurement. Several economic issues that need to be

considered are inflation, and the ups and downs of the country's economy. The socio-cultural aspect pays attention to the macro-environment that is being planned. Studies that can be done for this factor are about population growth, age distribution, or community culture. In the procurement of defense and security, it also considers the technological aspect, this alludes to innovation in technology. These factors include automation, research, and development. Then the environmental aspect which includes all the influences triggered by the surrounding environment, such as climate, weather, geographical conditions, global climate change, environmental damage, and others. And lastly, legal, where this aspect affects procurement that comes from existing regulations.

2.2 Offsets Policy in Indonesia

Offset is an arrangement between the Government and abroad arms suppliers to return a portion of the contract value to the buying country, as one of the terms of sale and purchase. Defense offset is the process of buying or investing reciprocally agreed upon by the manufacturer or supplier of weapons in return for an agreement to purchase military equipment and goods. Based on the type, offset is divided into two, direct offset or indirect offset. Direct offset is divided into three types, licensed production, co-production, and joint development or co-development. Meanwhile, indirect offsets are goods and services that are not directly related to the purchase of military products, but as an agreement in the process of buying and selling military and defense equipment. There are four types of indirect offsets, barter, counter-purchase, counter-investment, and buy back.

In direct offset, licensed production where the arms seller agrees to transfer his technology to the buying country. The partially or all of the weapon part can be produced in the buyer's country. Furthermore, joint production or co-production, occurs when buyers and sellers not only seek to procure armaments but also produce goods and services for military equipment together, by seeking joint marketing as well. The countries of the seller and the buyer are business partners. The other type is co-development, in which the producing country and the buying country seek to develop advanced defense equipment. In this type, the buying country has the advantage that it can actively adopt weapons technology either directly or indirectly, thereby gradually increasing the human resource capabilities of the buying country.

In direct offsets, the first type is barter, where the seller and buyer have an agreement on the process of buying and selling weapons, which can be paid for with non-military products by the buying country with a nominal value equivalent to the price of weapons. Second, counter-purchase, in which the weapons supplier agrees to buy non-military products or find buyers for non-military products with an agreed nominal value of the purchased weapons price. Third, counter-investment, in which the arms seller agrees to find a third party willing to invest in the buyer's country at a certain or agreed value. Fourth, buy back where the arms seller agrees to buy back or find a third party to buy the product for a certain period of time.

In Indonesia, the offset policy regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation No. 30 of 2015 which contains tradeoffs, local content and offsets, and the foreign arms procurement. Tradeoff is a reciprocal trading activity. The tradeoffs are agreed between the two countries with a minimum return value of 85% of the contract value. Local content and offset is a common requirement to support local composition or resources on imported weapons with minimum value is 35%.

2.3 Procurement Management

Procurement management is management to obtain goods or services that are part of system production in supply chain management. Procurement management is an important for companies because of the increasingly fierce competition where there is a role for the availability of the goods needed. From a situation that is constantly changing, the procurement cannot be underestimated. Competitive advantage in procurement management is obtained from advantages in better quality supplies with more economical prices or costs, and this becomes a strategic strength. The function of procurement is purchasing, trade-in, leasing, or material transfer. In other words, procurement is a business process in selecting of resources, ordering and obtaining goods or services. In general, procurement activity [1]:

- a. Selection of suppliers and subcontractors
- b. Fostering appropriate relationships with suppliers and subcontractors, both long-term partnerships or short-term transactional. In a more detailed, this section also opens opportunities for the formation of new collaborations such as R&D (Research & Development) activities, capacity building, investment and alliances.
- c. Implementation of tools or technology in every procurement activity. Today, many companies are implementing e-procurement (electronic procurement) for easier and faster access.
- d. Maintenance of material data that is usually needed by the company and data of suppliers and subcontractors who provide it.

- e. Make purchases, either routine purchases or purchases through auctions.
- f. Performance evaluation of suppliers and subcontractors.

The Arms procurement policy in Indonesia regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation Number 17 of 2014 concerning the implementation of the procurement of the main weapon system equipment. The regulation explains that the arms procurement must use domestic production. If the domestic defense industry has not fulfilled it, the foreign arms procurement can be carried out. The principles for the procurement are efficient, effective, transparent in budget management, guarantee confidentiality, be able to compete, be fair and non-discriminatory, and accountable. Procurement of foreign defense equipment must also meet several requirements, that are [2]:

- a. Have not or cannot be produce in domestic defense industry
- b. Involve the participation of the domestic defense industry
- c. Transfer technology obligations
- d. Guarantee the absence of embargoes, political conditionality and barriers to use.
- e. Minimum local content and offset 35%.

III. Research methodology

The design of this research is descriptive qualitative method. Descriptive research is research that observes problems systematically and accurately on a fact and the nature of a particular object. The concept of descriptive terms is not just data collection, tabulation and data narration. Descriptive research methods have a broader understanding and characteristics which focus on current and actual problems and the data obtained are compiled, explained and analyzed. This is called analytical descriptive [3]. Analytical descriptive method explains by describing based on data that has been taken objectively without any particular modification. By using descriptive qualitative methods, researchers can explore and understand the problem more clearly.

Data collection in this research comes from primary and secondary data. Primary data is based on interviews conducted within the Ministry of Defense. Selection of informants based on considerations and research objectives (purposive) [4]. The informants are the persons related to the object of research who have insight and information regarding to the foreign arms procurement. Secondary data comes from data collection to arms procurement.

IV. Result and Discussion

The arms procurement is regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation No. 17 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of the arms procurement. The regulation contains provisions regarding the procurement of defense and security equipment within the Ministry of Defense. There are many requirements that must be met in procuring. In Article 5 it is explained, if the arms procurement cannot be fulfilled by the domestic industry, the foreign arms procurement can be carried out. The regulation in article 72 also contains requirements for the Offset minimum 35%. Furthermore, the arms procurement is regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation No. 30 of 2015 concerning Tradeoff, Local Content and Offsets in Foreign Arms Procurement. Then for the counter-trade mechanism, it is regulated in the Government Regulation No. 76 of 2014 concerning the Counter-Trade Mechanism in Foreign Arms Procurement.

In arms procurement, the government has to decide on what to buy? Government has to decide upon the need and performance requirements of the weapon system, which are vague, change and evolve over time and differ between stakeholders [5]. Specifications are key to determining the technical progress, risks and uncertainties of the procurement [6]. The arms procurement process cannot be separated from the role of the government as a policy maker, regulation and implementer of procurement. In foreign procurement, it is necessary to have an offset as a procurement requirement which can be one way to encourage the independence of the defense industry. In the implementation and design of the offset, agreed by two countries in which the political and diplomatic relations of the two countries are very important. It is unlikely that two countries that have a dispute will cooperate in the procurement of weapons to strengthen their country's defense.

Therefore, arms procurement should be examined in its totality, not only focusing on some aspects of it, in order to get sense of why "suboptimal" results or results that do not fit into the declared principles of procurement agency or government [7]. When the decision is made for what to buy and how to get it, the government has to decide upon the contractor, contract type and timing. A contractor has to be selected where the options are between using competition

and direct negotiation with a preferred supplier [6], which also involves decision about contract type, agreements, and offset.

In the process of arms procurement, it will influence by strategic environment, like politics, economic, social-culture, technology, environment, and law. In Indonesia political aspect, both domestic politics and global politics. Active free politics as a non-aligned country has a role in the foreign arms procurement where it can be a good opportunity or a threat. Where it is known that Indonesia is very neutral towards global politics, this can be an opportunity where it is possible for Indonesia to cooperate with any country. However, the challenge is that Indonesian diplomacy must be capable and have good relations. On the other hand, if Indonesia has poor diplomacy, there will be a threat of an embargo. In terms of global politics, it also quite influences the foreign arms procurement in Indonesia. Where the US-Russia political tensions have a considerable influence. There are several Russian companies that are blacklisted by America and this is quite disturbing to Indonesia arms procurement with Russia.

The economic aspect has a high enough influence. The increasing level of the economy will affect the level of weapons procurement, where the possibility of an increase in the budget will also increase. From year to year the defense budget is quite increasing. In 2020, Indonesia defense budget is US\$7600 (million) and in 2021 increase to US\$9200 (million). The increasing of defense budget cause the improvement and stability of the economy in Indonesia. Equipment cost is one of the considerations in purchasing. government tries to get the most benefit out of this information asymmetry. Moreover, the government is the sole buyer of the arms, monopsonic principal, while there are only limited number of firms present that could provide desired weapons system, which are monopolistic or oligopolistic agents, depending on the complexity of the weapons system [7].

The aim of the state of Indonesia is the welfare of its people, of course it becomes the main principle in every program implemented. In the arms procurement also considered the current social conditions of the community, which ones are important to prioritize and implement. In this Covid-19, social conditions being prioritized for the government. That main priority is enough to influence the arms procurement plan by the ministry of defense. Arms procurement which was originally carried out since 2020 but needs to be postponed until conditions improve.

Innovation technology is one thing that cannot be separated from today. Every country is competing to create the latest technology. Technological advances, especially in weapons, are an important requirement in maintaining national defense and territory. In addition to having a large number of personnel, national defense also requires good infrastructure to support it. Arms procurement is arguably an activity that has high secrecy, because one of them contains the technology used to maintain state security.

In the environmental aspect, Indonesia's geographical conditions are also a consideration in the procurement of defense and security systems. Procurement must adapt to Indonesia's natural conditions, not to the point that the procurement of defense and security equipment is carried out not according to the terrain and weather in Indonesia. In addition, climate change is also one of the things to be considered. In addition to innovating products with the latest and advanced technology, environmentally friendly products are also one of the influencing factors.

V. Conclusion

Based on the of data collection, the strategic environment that has an impact on the arms procurement. The aspects of political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, environmental and legal greatly affect the arms procurement. Arms procurement is also strongly influenced by policies and regulations related to defense offsets. Implementation of the regulation can provide benefits to the country both economically and technologically. The arms procurement can be carried out optimally if the six aspects are able to be utilized optimally in accordance with existing policies.

References

- [1] Pujawan, I Nyoman, Mahendrawati. Supply Chain Management. 3rd Edition. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi, 2017.
- [2] Regulation of The Minister of Defense Number 17 of 2014.
- [3] Mahmud. Metode Penelitian Pendidikan. Bandung: Pustaka Setia, 2011.
- [4] Sugiyono. Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif. Bandung: CV Alfabeta, 2008.
- [5] Smith, R. Military Economics: The Interaction of Power and Money. Hampshire New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009.
- [6] Hartley, K. Arms Industry, Procurement and Industrial Policies. In T. Sandler & K. Hartley (Eds.), Handbook of Defense Economics (Vol. 2, pp. 1140-1176). Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2007.
- [7] Kurc, Caglar. The Role of Culture and Politics in Arms Procurement. 2012.